

EMI INVESTIGATION OF A BURIED FOUNDATION: CASE STUDY ADDRESSING REMAINS OF A CONTROLLED DEMOLISHED BUILDING

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Introduction

The electromagnetic induction method was applied for tracing the remains of a buried foundation in an urban area, in a site where abundant sources of geophysical noise were known to exist and consequently, interferences were expected for this type of survey.

The position of the building remains was partly known due to a previous survey based on the Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) method (Chitea et al., 2019). By means of the ERT method, it was revealed that the normal pattern of the geological structure was highly distorted in the specific area. Following the interpretation of the high resolution ERT sections it was possible to estimate the footprint of an old “L” shape buried structure, formed by two unequal wings. However, that previous survey was not able to include the entire substructure, due to the limits imposed by modern infrastructure (most of which was buried, but it also included several iron-made pieces located at the earth surface), as well as due to the technical constraints of the adopted survey technique (the equipment used for electrical resistivity measurements required direct contact between electrodes and soil, therefore the survey was not continued in asphalt covered areas surrounding the domain for which the ERT had indicated building remains).

Another issue concerned by the previous results reported in the paper Chitea et al. (2019) referred to the material used for building the buried foundation, since 90 years ago, at the time of its construction, different technical solutions were available.

Therefore, for addressing the indicated uncertainties, another geophysical method – electromagnetic induction (EMI) - was adopted in order to complement the previous ERT results.

Methods

By using the electromagnetic induction method with a tool that operates at Low Induction Number (LIN), the variation of the induced field along the profiles - recorded by the receiver coil - is electronically split into the In-phase and out-of-phase/Quadrature component (90° phase shift with respect to the primary field). The low induction number approximation of the In-phase response prevalently has an induced magnetization fraction, therefore obeying the magneto-static equations similarly to the magnetic method, but with an active magnetic source (Guillemoteau et al., 2019), being in this assumption correlated directly with the subsoil magnetic susceptibility. The electrical conductivity ($E_{c,a}$) is estimated according to the following equation (McNeill, 1980):

$$EC_a = \frac{4}{\omega \mu_0 d^2} \frac{H_S^Q}{H_P}$$

H_S^Q represents the measured in-quadrature component of the secondary magnetic field at the receiver coil H_P primary magnetic field at the transmitter coil,

d is the spacing between the dipoles

μ_0 is the permeability of free space

$\omega = 2\pi f$ is angular frequency, where f is frequency.

The data field acquisition was performed in vertical dipole mode, the coils (transmitter and receiver) being positioned at a distance of 1m, and the adopted operating frequency was 14.5 KHz. The effective depth of exploration for this type of portable equipment was therefore restricted to 1.5m (Geonics, 2005), which allowed a good separation of the near-surface targets from possible deeper sources.

Fig. 1 Structural interpretation of the building foundation in the area of Wing “A” as interpreted from the ERT profile, evidence for the presence of reinforced concrete structural foundations and reinforced concrete columns and beams being provided by EMI measurements

Results

EMI measurements were deployed in the area where previous ERT measurements had outlined substructures suggesting the presence of a buried foundation. By analyzing the in-depth extent of the high resistivity anomalies, it resulted that the former building had been constructed with a demi-basement of ~2m height (Chitea et al., 2019) (Fig. 1). After the demolition, the underground space was filled with construction materials debris. The lateral extent of the resistive top layer was used to approximate the extent of each “wing”. The demolished building outline presented in Chitea et al., 2019 and in Figure 4 is accordingly estimated, its extent being possibly subject to errors of up to 2 m. The design of the footprint was also adjusted by using a black and white picture.

In order to have a recognizable pattern of the EMI signal for the buried construction debris, several EM lines measured in the target area were compared with the signal recorded over 2 profiles (EM V- Ec and EM U-K): the latter are located ~50-70m away, in the northern part, in an area which after analyzing the geophysical results was admitted to be “undisturbed” by anthropogenic works. A comparison for both parameters (electrical conductivity and magnetic susceptibility) is given in Fig. 2, revealing the signatures of the construction works along the profiles recorded over the area which includes buried debris derived from the controlled demolition of the building. For the electrical conductivity, the profiles measured in an “undisturbed location” indicated a general trend of 10 ± 5 mS/m. From the EM measurements, it was noticed that buried debris zones exhibited a higher conductivity (>35 mS/m), characteristic for a soil domain shallower than 1.5m. When not associated with an anomaly specific to iron materials (dipolar

anomaly) on the magnetic susceptibility diagrams, extreme conductivity values (>70 mS/m), were assumed to reflect increased moisture contents.

Fig. 2 Two profiles (EM V-Ec and EM U-K) from the considered “undisturbed location”, are displayed in comparison with results from profiles EM 9-Ec, EM9-K, EM2-Ec and EM3-K, that are trending NW-SE along the area with buried debris. Data illustrated in these graphs were obtained by using a quasi-continuous acquisition mode, without soil-to-instrument contact

The magnetic susceptibility is another indicator that testifies the presence of the rubble. The undisturbed soil is characterized by the absence of magnetic properties, therefore the presence of ferromagnetic buried metals from the reinforced concrete walls or pipes that were not removed, are well delineated (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 4 Contour of the demolished building and EM – sector 3 (a). Maps of electrical conductivity (b) and magnetic susceptibility (c)

The area of interest was divided into several sectors, all having restricted extent due either to vegetation, or to anthropogenic works different from the target of this study. Both components (E_{ca} and K) were recorded simultaneously, the results obtained in Sector 3 being illustrated as a conductivity map (Fig. 4a) as well as a magnetic susceptibility map (Fig. 4c). Structural interpretation of the building foundation in the area of Wing “A” is in accordance with the results of the ERT profile (marked in Fig. 4a), evidence for the presence of reinforced concrete pillars being provided by EMI measurements.

Conclusions

The buried foundation was outlined by using the Quad-phase and In-phase ratio of the secondary to primary magnetic field components, which under the assumption of LIN correlates with the electrical conductivity (E_{ca}) and magnetic susceptibility (K) of the soil.

The E_{Ca} value is a weighted average across the 1.5m soil thickness. Low conductivity anomalies (40-70 mS/m for EM-Sector 3 – Fig. 4) correlate well with the buried foundation walls (marked as A – Figure 4a), while in the magnetic susceptibility map this structure could not be delineated.

The anomaly marked as “B” in Fig. 4a & 4b is an example of the effect given by ferromagnetic material, testifying for the use of metallic rebars in the main structural elements of the building, as components for the reinforced structural framing – concrete foundation and pillars reinforced with metal rebar cages and nets. The anomaly observed in the area marked as “C” is due to the effect of a ferromagnetic material used for the vent cap visible at the soil surface in close vicinity. Due to its interference, it is difficult to isolate the signal from buried remains in this area, which according to previous ERT measurements is part of the Wing B, having also an extension of ~2m towards south in the area of its junction with “Wing A”.

The electrical conductivity values along “Line D” fall in the same range as those associated to the foundation wall (marked as A), suggesting a possible internal wall that could have been built up for delimiting the basement. The extent of the EM sector 3 towards North was limited due to shrubbery plants, therefore the high conductivity anomaly observed in the E marked rectangle is most likely associated with an increased moisture content in the soil, given that the susceptibility map configuration precludes the presence of ferromagnetic material in that area.

References

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